

Personality, preferences, and self-selection into PhD programs: How does fit with program demands affect mental health and productivity of junior researchers? A pilot study.

Christiane Schwieren, Cosima Steck, Feriha Demir, Helke Hillebrand

Heidelberg University, Germany

Abstract

Economic theory of job selection predicts that people choose jobs based on their knowledge about own characteristics and the characteristics required to perform well on the job and, ideally, to like the job. This mechanism is called self-selection, and focuses on the choices made by potential employees, given the contracts offered by the potential employer and beliefs about own fit with the requirements for the job. Assuming that the same mechanism is at work in the selection into a PhD, we aim at an understanding whether the contracts offered by PhD programs/universities attract the people with the best fit for the task at hand, and whether those who select themselves into those programs do have correct beliefs about their fit in the system and the job. Good person-job fit then leads not only to higher levels of productivity, but also to employee well-being – good mental health.

We conducted a survey among PhD students in Germany, to test how certain personality factors and preferences relate to well-being in the PhD program and mental health of the researcher. We consider a multitude of characteristics of the PhD program, most notably the field, whether it is a formal program or not, the financing of the PhD time and, importantly, the stage of the PhD the respondent is in. Controlling for gender, socio-economic background and nationality, we correlate the decision in (non-incentivized) measures for risk-, time, and social preferences with outcome variables: Mental health, well-being more generally, progress in the PhD. The results help us to better understand who thrives under which conditions and who doesn't. The data on tenure in the program give us an (imperfect due to sample size issues and panel nature of the data) idea what characterizes the combination of person and program characteristics that leads to leaving the program early. The survey is a pilot for a larger, cross-national study on the same topic. It's analysis and discussion will allow us to come up with the best possible design for the larger study, focusing only on the most meaningful aspects both from a theoretical and an empirical perspective.